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BRIDGING DIGITAL DIVIDE IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

Title: **BRIDGING DIGITAL DIVIDE IN PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SCHOOLS**

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Degree: **MASTER OF ARTS IN EDUCATION**

Major: **ADMINISTRATION AND SUPERVISION**

Institution: **OSIAS COLLEGES, INC.**

This study investigated the digital divide between private and public schools students in Holy Trinity College of Technology, Inc employing a descriptive-comparative research design to objectively understand digital access difference. Through random sampling techniques involving 60 respondents from both public and private schools, a survey questionnaire on digital access of students was employed to capture demographic information and assess perceived digital access challenges.

In Paniqui, Tarlac, many students have smartphones, but there is difference in owning laptops and computers, with private school students likely having better access. Majority in the public schools have a family income of less than 5,000 while it is 5,000-10,000 in the private school. The gap between public and private schools is clear in various digital aspects like internet, software, literacy, and online resources. Private schools consistently have more access and resources. Hence, digital accessibility is not a problem in private schools and quite a problem in public schools. There is therefore a significant difference on accessibility between public and private school in terms of hardware, internet connectivity, software tools, digital literacy and online educational resources. To bridge this gap, public schools aim for government funding for technology upgrades, while private schools seek partnerships for technology donations. These efforts highlight ongoing plans to make sure all students, no matter where they study, have equal access to digital tools and learning resources in the Philippines.

Forge a partnership between public schools and the local government (LGU) to

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provide free internet access in the public spaces like schools, libraries and community centers to help the students especially those from low-income families. Continue reaching out to individual students by providing free community access to computers at public schools. Establish linkages with local government officials particularly the governor, municipal mayor, barangay captain and SK`s alongside the non-governance (NGOs) for gadgets and connectivity. Implement the proposed strategies to overcome digital divide.

Keywords: hardware, connectivity, software, technology

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